

TEACHERS' DRUG PREVENTION FACILITATION AND ELEMENTARY LEARNERS' CAPACITY

ZOILA I. NAVARRO

Abstract. The study unfolded the extent of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program and further determining elementary learners' receptive capacity in Montevista District, Davao de Oro. The study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, where it utilized adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of school environment, religious and cultural influences, community engagement, parents' participation and classroom climate is moderately extensive, and likewise, learners' receptive capacity in terms of comprehension and understanding, attitude and behavior change, application of knowledge and skills, engagement and active participation, and openness to information is moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program and learners' receptive capacity. Indicators of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of classroom climate, school environment, parents' participation, community engagement, and religious and cultural influences suggest significant influential over learners' receptive capacity. Future research may evaluate different approaches, strategies, and interventions in drug prevention programs. This can include innovative instructional methods, integration of technology, or targeted interventions for specific populations to identify effective practices and enhance the receptivity and effectiveness of the programs.

KEY WORDS

1. teachers' drug prevention 2. facilitation 3. receptive capacity

1. Introduction

Education is a powerful weapon in the war on drugs. Each school, each community, each hoe has a vital role to play in helping young people remain drug free. Educating young people about the hazards of alcohol and other drug use and arming them with skills that deter drug use is an important competent of the nation's war against drugs. To combat learner drug use most effectively, the entre community must be involved such as parents, schools, students, law enforcement authorities, religious and community organizations. Each of these groups must unite behind a consistent message that illegal drug use is wrong and harmful. Schools are uniquely situated to play a major role in prevention because young people spend much of their time in school because schools are a major influence in transmitting appropriate standards of behavior. Schools can contribute to the national prevention efforts, not only by presenting

accurate information about drugs, but also by developing and enforcing firm, consistent policies that discourage their use and sale. Further information about how to establish a comprehensive drug prevention program is contained in the policies of academics and education department (Rigg and Menendez, 2018). Across the globe, the use of some drugs by school-age youths has declined recently, drug use continues to be a grave problem. Alcohol use, for example, continues at unacceptably high levels among high school students and in some communities, crack cocaine has drawn children into a deadly world of drug dealing and drug use. Countries face an unprecedented assault by new drugs as well as drugs that are significantly more powerful than those available 10 to 15 years ago. These drugs are affecting all segments of society (Chang, et.al., 2015). In the Philippines, the educational programs are based on the notion of drug addiction as a human problem and are designed by an international education committee which seeks to stimulate participation of individuals and groups by making them aware to stimulate participation of individuals and groups by making them aware of the problem's causes. An integrated action plan was developed during an international meeting on education in prevention of drug abuse emphasizes the need for specific drug education in children's institutional programs, parent groups and existing community programs, as well as for creation of new activities for youth encouraging mental and physical health, value development, flexibility, responsibility, communication with parents, and a sense of community. Education programs include a comprehensive pilot projects for the communities, a youth program with discussions of the problem, a workshop for leaders and courses to inform parents of their responsibilities toward their children, a special training course for social service workers, and the like (Benard, and Marchall, 2015). In Montevista District Schools, Davao de Oro Division, developed a program intervention focused on the role of school structure and or parent-student and teacher-student relationships in prevention, as well as on the necessity of teacher and health professional training and on the revision of educational directives in drug matters. Further, information services are provided to the community and stakeholders along with numerous community organizations during drug prevention week as well as other interventions for the campaign. However, in the school-based management of implementation, classrooms and the learning environment are highly observed to have high risk in its effectiveness in making learners intensify the awareness. Results of the campaigns seem not to affect the young learners' awareness and with parents' participation are observed to be in low returns. Only by working together, every school, and every community can we make our children aware that drug use is dangerous. Schools in Montevista District has to augment the campaign through facilitation of drug prevention. Schools may provide the basics for starting or expanding drug education which includes information about drugs, teachers skills and child growth and development through integration, suggestions on working with parents and the community. Further, the drug prevention message into the general school curriculum through a process by which teachers in a variety of subject areas present drug prevention lessons using skills and information appropriate to their specific subjects. The success of any classroom program often is linked to appropriate teacher training. In-service training for principals and teachers on how to use drug prevention is vital. This has to attempt provide enough background information for lessons and activities so that all teachers will feel confident teaching about drug prevention. Thus, this research is conceptualize to add on to the advocacy in school policies and to the implementation of intensifying the integration of facilitation on drug prevention and

abuse in the schools of Montevista District, thus, this paper was conducted.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the technical method and its process in the conduct of the study. This includes the selection of the design of the study, the respondents and its sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, and the ethical consideration and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are considered essentials to assume appropriateness and correctness to produce sound data process collection, analysis and interpretation.

2.1. Research Design—This study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. A correlational research design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them. A correlation reflects the strength and/or direction of the relationship between two (or more) variables. The direction of a correlation can be either positive or negative. (Pallant, 2020). Findings from correlational research can be used to determine prevalence and relationships among variables, and to forecast events from current data and knowledge. In spite of its many uses, prudence is required when using the methodology and analysing data. On the other hand, this type of research tries to extrapolate from the analysis of existing phenomena, policies, or other entities in order to predict something that has not been tried, tested, or proposed before (Gujarati, 2020). In this study, indicators under independent variable, classroom climate, school environment, parents' participation, community engagement and religious and cultural influences are used to estimate the extent of drug prevention facilitation which are assumed to be correlated with dependent variable, where its indicators are learners' receptive capacity in terms of openness to information; comprehension and understanding; engagement and active participation; application of knowledge and skills; and attitude and behavior change in Montevista District, davao de Oro. Using the design mentioned, it is assumed that variables along with its

indicators mentioned, the researcher empirically provide evidence that presented hypothesis shall be null and void in nature.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Teachers of Montevista District, Davao de Oro Division. She used Raosoft sample size calculator, where a total of 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective school within the mentioned District. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face to face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections, they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. As much as possible, these teacher-respondents were teachers teaching three years and above in the public school service, in the respective schools to measure their competence in responding to the queries of the study and how they performed and contributed to the betterment of the schools and to the learners' absorptive capacity on drug abuse prevention program given new normal learning system during SY 2022-2023. Further, they have frequently engaged in various seminars and trainings including SLAC sessions on the pedagogies in integrating drug prevention program in the school management system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents and even observance to health protocol was strictly implemented based on the Executive Order 31 S

2020, to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This research study used a self-made survey instrument. The researcher took time in gathering and reading reviews of related literature to come up with concepts for the content of the instrument. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literatures as argued by the authors. There were two parts of the survey questionnaire which consists of measuring the extent teachers’ drug prevention program facilitation in terms of classroom climate, school environment, parents’ participation, community engagement and religious and cultural influences. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the extent of learners’ receptive capacity in terms of open-

ness to information; comprehension and understanding; engagement and active participation; application of knowledge and skills; and attitude and behavior change. Contents of the statements of the survey were placed in the contexts based on the definition of the variables. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at .05 level of confidence and generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.887 which means that 88.7 percent level of confidence of the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs (Pallant 2010). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of teachers’ critical thinking abilities. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The drug prevention facilitation is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The drug prevention facilitation is often-times manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The drug prevention facilitation is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The drug prevention facilitation is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The drug prevention facilitation is not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The preceding statements steps explain the data gathering procedure steps where the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The statements are based on the policies and guidelines of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the existing guidelines of the IATF to ensure safe and lower risks in the gathering of pertinent data most especially in the current full face to face interaction. Permission to conduct the study. On the second week of January 2023, the re-

searcher started to conceptualize the contents and objective of the thesis proposal. She then, prepares documents such as letter requests in the conduct of the study. The research study underwent and adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004), and health protocol as provided by the policy of IATF. As soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote and sent a letter of permission to the office of

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation (Learners' Receptive Capacity)

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The learners' receptive capacity is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The learners' receptive capacity is often-times manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The learners' receptive capacity is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The learners' receptive capacity is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The learners' receptive capacity is not manifested

the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao de Oro, through channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study within the schools of Montevista District Schools. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. The researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process which were sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses, and for respondents who do not have access to internet. Likewise a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets were given to each of them. Once done, link was sent, and right away responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the ap-

proval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed in data gathering which commenced on the third week of January 2023. Collation and statistical treatment of data. Results of the preliminary analysis were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of February 2023. For coaching and in terms of statistical treatment the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician for providing technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study, sometime on the fourth week of February 2023, and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results on the second week of March 2023.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of teachers' drug prevention facilitation, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of learners' receptive capacity in Montevista, Davao de Oro. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength / direction significant relationship between the extent of teachers' drug prevention facilitation and the extent of learners'

receptive capacity in Montevista, Davao de Oro. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of extent of teachers' drug prevention facilitation that significantly influence learners' receptive capacity in Montevista, Davao de Oro (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were treated using the Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations then followed when results yield.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered. Tabular and textual presentation is presented to make more meaningful in the analysis and drawing out of implications. This further shows evidence to support the claim posed in the hypothesis.

Teachers' Facilitation on School-Based Drug Prevention Program

Teachers' facilitation in school-based drug prevention programs is a crucial component of successful implementation. Teachers play a pivotal role in creating a supportive and engaging learning environment for students. They guide the implementation process by ensuring that the program's objectives, content, and activities align with the needs and characteristics of their students. They also establish clear guidelines and expectations for student behavior and participation. Teachers serve as the primary point of contact for students, providing guidance, support, and encouragement throughout the program. In terms of content delivery, teachers act as facilitators, using various instructional strategies to present information on drug abuse, its consequences, and prevention strategies. They employ interactive teaching methods such as discussions, role-plays, and group activities to actively engage students and promote critical thinking. Teachers also adapt their instructional approaches to accommodate diverse learning styles and address the specific needs of individual students. Furthermore, teachers foster a safe and non-judgmental space for students to discuss their thoughts, concerns, and experiences related to drug abuse. They promote open dialogue and encourage students to ask questions, seek clarification, and share their perspectives. By creating an environment of trust and respect, teachers help students develop a deeper understanding of the issues surrounding drug abuse and prevention. Teachers also play a vital role in monitoring and assessing student progress in the drug prevention program. They track students' participation, evaluate their understanding of

the material, and provide constructive feedback. Teachers identify areas where students may require additional support or intervention and offer appropriate resources or referrals to relevant support services when needed. Lastly, teachers act as positive role models by embodying the values and behaviors promoted in the drug prevention program. They demonstrate healthy decision-making, responsible behavior, and resilience in the face of challenges. Through their own actions, teachers inspire and motivate students to adopt positive attitudes and behaviors towards drug prevention. In conclusion, teachers' facilitation in school-based drug prevention programs encompasses various responsibilities, including program implementation, content delivery, creating a supportive environment, monitoring student progress, and serving as positive role models. Their active involvement and commitment contribute significantly to the effectiveness of these programs, empowering students to make informed decisions and leading to positive outcomes in drug prevention efforts.

Table 1 shows the extent of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of classroom climate. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Set up behavior management processes (3.40) is oftentimes manifested, while, Teachers' develop high expectations of learning for students (3.30) and Comfortable physical space where children are able to sit comfortably, see and understand what their teacher is saying, as well as socialise with their fellow classmates (3.15) are sometimes manifested, and Use Effective, Evidence-Based Teaching And Learning Practices (2.20) and Comfortable physical space where children are

able to sit comfortably, see and understand what their teacher is saying, as well as socialise with their fellow classmates (2.20) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.85 denotes extent of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of classroom climate is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Classroom or learning climate refers to the " intellectual, social, emotional, and physical environments in which our stu-

dents learn." (Ambrose, S. A., Bridges, M. W., DiPietro, M., Lovett, M. C.,2010) as cited by Benard and Marshall (2015). Research suggests significant relationships between classroom climate and such matters as student engagement, behavior, self'-efficacy, achievement, and social and emotional development, principal leadership style, stages of educational reform, teacher burnout, and overall quality of school life.

Table 1. Extent of Teachers' Facilitation on School-based Drug Prevention Program in Terms of Classroom Climate

No	Classroom Climate	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Comfortable physical space where children are able to sit comfortably, see and understand what their teacher is saying, as well as socialise with their fellow classmates	3.15	Moderately Extensive
2	Teachers' develop high expectations of learning for students	3.30	Moderately Extensive
3	Set up behavior management processes	3.40	Extensive
4	Use Effective, Evidence-Based Teaching And Learning Practices	2.20	Less Extensive
5	Comfortable physical space where children are able to sit comfortably, see and understand what their teacher is saying, as well as socialise with their fellow classmates	2.20	Less Extensive
Overall Mean		2.85	Moderately Extensive

Having a comfortable physical space where children are able to sit comfortably, see and understand what their teacher is saying, as well as socialise with their fellow classmates is one of the major components of a conducive learning environment. Classroom environment is a blend of the social, emotional, and instruc-

tional elements of the class. Research shows that many aspects of your classroom environment can affect student motivation and that students who are more motivated, put more effort into learning activities. An open classroom climate, one where diverse opinions and discussion of social and political issues with regards

to drug prevention are welcome, promotes civic development among youth and fosters critical consciousness. Critical consciousness, defined as the capacity to recognize societal inequity along with the motivation and action taken to challenge such inequity and promote positive social change, also engenders civic development and engagement. Advancements in critical consciousness measurement and changes in the sociopolitical climate over the past two decades suggest the need to reexamine the effects of open classroom climate on critical consciousness. Rapa, et.al., (2022) explored the extent to which an open classroom climate is associated with critical consciousness in a contemporary, diverse sample of preadolescent and adolescent youth. Results suggest open classroom climate is linked with the reflection, motivation, and action dimensions of critical consciousness. Implications for promoting an open classroom climate and critical consciousness are discussed. Kaplan (2022) described how intra- and interdisciplinary learning experiences can activate the interests and capabilities among children in their early years regarding drug prevention as integration in classroom instruction. A developmental sequence delineates a series of stage-by-stage experiences describing the skill and content to be introduced and mastered in the teaching and learning process, which include developing readiness and receptivity, intradisciplinary thinking and learning, and interdisciplinary thinking and learning. The recognized differences among learners, the qualities inherent in providing advanced learning skills and concepts, and the development and reinforcement of basic and fundamental skills provides a readiness for more sophisticated learning in

the early years. The importance of promoting understanding and facilitating the display of interests and capabilities among children in the early years can be activated by intra- and interdisciplinary learning experiences.

Table 2 extent of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of school environment. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Establishes relationships among students and staff/teachers, learning and teaching emphasis, values and norms, and shared approaches and practices (4.00) and Teachers and staff to implement effective strategies and programs through professional development (3.45) are oftentimes manifested, while, Improves academic achievement, test scores, grades, and engagement and helps reduce the negative effects of poverty on academic achievement (3.35), Build learning environments that are healthy and engaging (3.00) and Implements availability of facilities, classrooms practices, school-based health supports, and disciplinary policies and practices (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.43 denotes extent of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of school environment is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. Environment, which is defined as family beliefs and attitudes, peer group, community, and more, is also believed to heavily influence addiction because these are typically the factors that lead an individual to try drugs or alcohol initially. Drug education and the school environment usually focuses on influencing students' values, attitudes, knowledge and skills so they make healthier decisions about alcohol and other drugs.

Osher, Neiman and Williamson (2020) claimed that when done reliably and efficiently, measuring school climate can help improve schools' vital signs and help state boards of

education realize their goals and objectives for the system as a whole. Moreover, because it is as consequential to schools as checking heart rates and blood pressure are to humans, schools

Table 2. Extent of Teachers’ Facilitation on School-based Drug Prevention Program in Terms of School Environment

No	School Environment	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Establishes relationships among students and staff/teachers, learning and teaching emphasis, values and norms, and shared approaches and practices	4.00	Extensive
2	Teachers and staff to implement effective strategies and programs through professional development	3.45	Extensive
3	Build learning environments that are healthy and engaging	3.30	Moderately Extensive
4	Improves academic achievement, test scores, grades, and engagement and helps reduce the negative effects of poverty on academic achievement	3.35	Moderately Extensive
5	Implements availability of facilities, classrooms practices, school-based health supports, and disciplinary policies and practices	3.00	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.43	Extensive

should always use climate measures for planning and continuous improvement. School climate data can be used appropriately as a metric for statewide accountability as well. Drug prevention must be the priority to ensure that learners are dwelling in a safe and conducive to learn environment. In addition, school mindfulness is the maintenance of individual and collective attention to organizational operations in a school. Mindful teachers and school principals develop appropriate organizational behaviors by examining all details of all practices in the school in terms of their originality with different expert opinions. In this research, the organizational mechanisms that can contribute to the development of organizational mindfulness have been investigated. For this purpose, the effects on school mindfulness of information-sharing practices at administrative and peer levels, which are organizational subprocesses of the collaborative

organizational climate, were investigated. A collaborative school climate includes important organizational mechanisms that have the potential to improve school mindfulness, especially through organizational practices that encourage the sharing of knowledge. The findings of this study, contain important implications for collaborative organizational processes that includes drug prevention that have the potential to improve mindfulness among school principals and faculty members, such that early learners are protected with harmful effects through drug abuse and prevention. Further, school climate has received considerable attention in the literature and educational policy as a potential target for school improvement and school safety efforts including drug prevention. Bradshaw, et.l., (2021) provided a critical review and synthesis of the literature on school climate, with a particular focus on topics related to measurement, data

collection, analysis, as well as prevention and promotion planning. Authors also attend to potential mechanisms of changing school and community culture and behavioral norms in relation to school climate promotion and implementation efforts. They concluded that by identifying future directions for research related to school climate and highlight the role school psychologists can play in improving measurement, promoting the use of data-based decision making which leverages various sources of information on school climate, implementing school-wide programming, and considering the influence of school climate more broadly on implementation of drug prevention.

Table 3 shows the extent of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of parents' participation. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Develop

Healthy family roles and behaviors include holding the loved one accountable for their behavior and creating rewards for positive choices. Family members may attend support groups with their loved one or attend their own support groups for families of addicts. Youth are less likely to use addictive substances if their parents talk early and often about the risks, establish clear rules and consequences, and regularly monitor their activities. Active involvement and support of caring adults are both critical in the prevention of youth substance abuse. On the other hand, when children are being neglected due to parental substance abuse, developmental problems often arise, such as speech delays, malnutrition, and cognitive functioning issues. Parental drug use during pregnancy can result in birth defects, attachment problems and drug-affected newborns. Drugs and alcohol inhibit a parent's ability to function in a parental role and may lessen impulse control, allowing parents to behave abusively. Children in these homes

healthy friendships and relationships with children and knowing their daily activities (3.40) is oftentimes manifested, while, Ability to discuss freely about drug abuse and its prevention (3.30) and Asks in a nonjudgmental, open-ended way, so you're more likely to get an honest response (3.25) are sometimes manifested, and Take time in helping children and young people understand that all drugs, legal and illegal, have the potential to cause harm, and that the drug experience is because of many factors including the person, the drug and the environment (2.40) and Actively participates in community campaigns aimed at stopping substance abuse within the community (2.00) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.87 denotes extent of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of parents' participation is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

may suffer from a variety of physical, mental, and emotional health problems at a greater rate than do children in the general population. Family functioning is closely related to individual drug use. Studies have shown that individuals are less likely to have problem behaviors when they interact well with family members, especially their parents. Song, Qian and Goodnight (2019) aimed to understand the extent to which parent involvement, community involvement, and schoolwide violence-prevention initiatives reduced school violence, considering school racial/ethnic compositions and crime levels and the absence of drug prevention and abuse in schools. Results revealed that higher levels of parent involvement in school activities were associated with fewer incidents of school violence for elementary and middle schools, whereas more community involvement in school efforts predicted more school violence. Staff training and student-oriented prevention programs did not relate with school violence in primary and

Table 3. Extent of Teachers’ Facilitation on School-based Drug Prevention Program in Terms of Parents’ Participation

No	Parents’ Participation	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Ability to discuss freely about drug abuse and its prevention	3.30	Moderately Extensive
2	Asks in a nonjudgmental, open-ended way, so you’re more likely to get an honest response	3.25	Moderately Extensive
3	Take time in helping children and young people understand that all drugs, legal and illegal, have the potential to cause harm, and that the drug experience is because of many factors including the person, the drug and the environment	2.40	Less Extensive
4	Develop healthy friendships and relationships with children and knowing their daily activities	3.40	Extensive
5	Actively participates in community campaigns aimed at stopping substance abuse within the community	2.00	Less Extensive
Overall Mean		2.87	Moderately Extensive

secondary schools. Additionally, parent involvement served as a protective factor for schools with high levels of racial/ethnic minority composition and/or located in neighborhoods with high crime levels. Sylaj (2020) analyzed the involvement of parents in school and the information of drug prevention as an influential factor on this process. The other purpose was to examine teachers’, parents’ and school principals attitudes on the prevention of violence between students in school. The results support the assumptions of the study, by showing that the information has a positive link with statistical significance with the level of the parents’ involvement in school and drug prevention. On the other side there exist two contradicting ascertainties between parents and the school about their perceptions and practices of infor-

mation. The interviews have discovered a very concerning case and the fact that a part of the psychological violence between students does not get reported to the family or school.

Table 4 shows the extent of teachers’ facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of community engagement. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Works with community partners to develop, adopt and implement policies; and support system and environmental change to prevent chronic disease, injuries, and chronic conditions (4.10) is often-times manifested, while, Provide feedback in the implementation of the local barangay to parents and school management system (3.30) and Inclusion of the intensification of drug abuse and prevention in the locality (3.20) are some-

times manifested, and Track Drug Prevention coordinators in the community and collaborate with Teachers in the School (2.20) and Engage with continuous improvement of the planning and implementation cycle in collaboration with local constituents (2.00) are rarely manifested.

The overall mean rating of 2.96 denotes extent of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of community engagement is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 4. Extent of Teachers' Facilitation on School-based Drug Prevention Program in Terms of Community Engagement

No	Community Engagement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Works with community partners to develop, adopt and implement policies; and support system and environmental change to prevent chronic disease, injuries, and chronic conditions	4.10	Extensive
2	Inclusion of the intensification of drug abuse and prevention in the locality	3.20	Moderately Extensive
3	Track Drug Prevention coordinators in the community and collaborate with Teachers in the School	2.20	Less Extensive
4	Provide feedback in the implementation of the local barangay to parents and school management system	3.30	Moderately Extensive
5	Engage with continuous improvement of the planning and implementation cycle in collaboration with local constituents	2.00	Less Extensive
Overall Mean		2.96	Moderately Extensive

Communities need to plan and implement research-based prevention programs to address Substance Abuse. Actions to be taken by Communities include identifying, assessing needs and community readiness and motivating the community to take action. One practical strategy that can be implemented by the community is to involve youth people or organisations to ensure that anti-substance abuse campaigns are effective. The main objective of this campaign is to build a community, especially among youth

people that is free of drug and alcohol abuse. Community-wide prevention, targeted at alcohol and other drug abuse, is defined as comprehensive programs targeted at multiple systems, using multiple strategies that include involving and training impactors, providing information, developing life skills, creating alternatives, and influencing policy. Community Based Treatment refers to a specific integrated model of treatment for people affected by drug use and dependence in the community which provides a

continuum of care from outreach and low threshold services, through detoxification and stabilisation to aftercare and integration, including maintenance pharmacotherapy. It involves the coordination of a number of health, social and other non-specialist services needed to meet the patient's needs. Strong support is also given to the patient's family and the community to address the drug and alcohol problems in their complexity and to ensure efficient and long-term results. Prevention in the community and at the workplace is a vital component in substance use disorder treatment and management. Mobilizing the community, creating awareness that addiction to substances is a disease, that it is treatable and that treatment is available are all essential. A cost-effective prevention and treatment approach plays a major role in creating drug free communities. Workplace prevention policies to prevent and manage substance use disorders leads to safer work environments, better motivated teams of workers and a productive workforce (Malick, 2018). Holder, et.al., (2020) Youth use of harmful legal products, including inhaling or ingesting everyday household products, prescription drugs, and over-the-counter drugs, constitutes a growing health problem for American society. As such, a single targeted approach to preventing such a drug problem in a community is unlikely to be sufficient to reduce use and abuse at the youth population level. Therefore, the primary focus of the author

There are several ways that culture can affect religion. First, culture can influence what religious beliefs we hold. Second, culture can shape how we practise our religion. And third, culture can impact the way we think about and experience religious concepts like God, prayer, and ritual. Culture can sometimes be a protective factor against substance use. For example, in the *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, it was noted that higher ethnic identity was associ-

is on an innovative, comprehensive, community-based prevention intervention. The intervention described here is based upon prior research that has a potential of preventing youth use of alcohol and other legal products. It builds upon three evidence-based prevention interventions from the substance abuse field: community mobilization, environmental strategies, and school-based prevention education intervention.

Table 5 shows the extent of facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of religious and cultural influences. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Facilitation considers learners belief and ethnicity (4.15) and Learners' values and family orientation are highly considered (4.00) are oftentimes manifested, while, Diverse religious and spiritual beliefs can impact learners experiences and influence their decisions regarding treatment (3.30) is sometimes manifested, and Culture can affect how children build values, language, belief systems, and an understanding of themselves as individuals and as members of society (2.30) and Respects learners religious views, values, beliefs, indigenous practices, and languages (2.20) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.19 denotes extent of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of religious and cultural influences is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

ated with lower past-month drug use among African American, Hispanic and Multiracial youth. Many Christian denominations disapprove of the use of most illicit drugs. Many denominations permit the moderate use of socially and legally acceptable drugs like alcohol, caffeine and tobacco. Some Christian denominations permit smoking tobacco, while others disapprove of it (Ma, et.al., 2017). On the other hand, the influence of culture on health is vast.

Table 5. Extent of Teachers’ Facilitation on School-based Drug Prevention Program in Terms of Religious and Cultural Influences

No	Religious and Cultural Influences	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Facilitation considers learners belief and ethnicity	4.15	Extensive
2	Learners’ values and family orientation are highly considered	4.00	Extensive
3	Respects learners religious views, values, beliefs, indigenous practices, and languages	2.20	Less Extensive
4	Diverse religious and spiritual beliefs can impact learners experiences and influence their decisions regarding treatment	3.30	Moderately Extensive
5	Culture can affect how children build values, language, belief systems, and an understanding of themselves as individuals and as members of society	2.30	Less Extensive
Overall Mean		3.19	Moderately Extensive

It affects perceptions of health, illness and death, beliefs about causes of disease, approaches to health promotion, how illness and pain are experienced and expressed, where patients seek help, and the types of treatment patients prefer. Religious belief and practice contribute substantially to the formation of personal moral criteria and sound moral judgment. Regular religious practice generally inoculates individuals against a host of social problems, including suicide, drug abuse, out-of-wedlock births, crime, and divorce. Culture may be thought of as a causal agent that affects the evolutionary process by uniquely human means. Religion, on the other hand, is considered a process of revelation and contains the concept of the "faithful" who receive the message of revelation (Song, et.al., 2019). Thus, religion is considered to be a part of culture and it acts as one among many forms of overtly expressing and experiencing spirituality that is inward, personal, subjective, transcendental, and unsystematic. In other

words, cultural values are seen as a foundation to religiosity. The relationship between culture and religion is revealed in the motivation and manifestation of cultural expression. If culture expresses how humans experience and understand the world; religion is a fundamental way in which humans experience and understand the world. Religion is a collection of cultural systems, belief systems, and worldviews that relate humanity to spirituality and, sometimes, to moral values. Many religions have narratives, symbols, traditions and sacred histories that are intended to give meaning to life or to explain the origin of life or the universe (Shin, et.al., 2022).

Table 6 shows the summary of facilitation on school-based drug prevention program. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: school environment (3.42) is oftentimes manifested, while, religious and cultural influences (3.21), community engagement (2.96),

parents' participation (2.87) and classroom climate (2.85) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.06 denotes extent of facilitation on school-based drug prevention program is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 6. Summary of the Teachers' School-based Drug Prevention Program

No	Teachers' Facilitation Skills on School-based Drug Prevention Program	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Classroom climate	2.85	Moderately Extensive
2	School environment	3.43	Extensive
3	Parents' participation	2.87	Moderately Extensive
4	Community engagement	2.96	Moderately Extensive
5	Religious and cultural influences	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.06	Moderately Extensive

One effective strategy for teachers is to incorporate drug prevention education into the curriculum. This can be done through dedicated lessons, workshops, or integration into existing subjects like health education or life skills classes. By providing accurate and age-appropriate information about drugs, their effects, and the risks associated with their use, teachers can empower students to make informed decisions and resist peer pressure. Teachers can also facilitate open and non-judgmental discussions about drugs and their impact. Creating a safe and supportive classroom environment where students feel comfortable sharing their thoughts and concerns allows for honest conversations. This enables teachers to address misconceptions, provide accurate information, and dispel myths surrounding drug use. Furthermore, teachers can collaborate with school counselors, administrators, and parents to establish a comprehensive drug prevention

program. This can involve organizing guest speakers, workshops, or awareness campaigns that focus on the dangers of drug abuse. By involving the entire school community, teachers can reinforce consistent messaging and create a culture of prevention and support. Additionally, teachers can be vigilant in identifying signs of drug use or related issues among their students. They can observe changes in behavior, academic performance, or social interactions that may indicate a student's involvement with drugs. Early intervention through appropriate channels, such as reporting concerns to school administrators or referring students to counseling services, can help prevent further harm and provide necessary support. Moreover, teachers should prioritize fostering positive relationships with their students. Building trust and rapport allows for open communication and increased receptiveness to drug prevention messages. By demonstrating care, empathy, and

support, teachers can create an environment that promotes students' well-being and reduces the likelihood of turning to drugs as a coping mechanism. In conclusion, teachers' facilitation of drug prevention plays a vital role in safeguarding students' well-being and promoting healthy choices. Through incorporating drug prevention education, engaging in open discussions, collaborating with stakeholders, and maintaining supportive relationships, teachers can effectively prevent and mitigate substance abuse among their students. By actively addressing this issue, teachers contribute to the overall health, safety, and success of their students.

Learners' Receptive Capacity Learners' receptive capacity, in the context of a drug prevention program, refers to their ability and willingness to engage with, absorb, and apply the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors promoted in the program. It encompasses their level of openness to information, comprehension and understanding of the material, active engagement and participation, and their readiness for attitude and behavior change. Receptive capacity is crucial in drug prevention programs as it determines the extent to which learners are able to internalize and benefit from the program's content. It reflects their receptiveness to learning about the risks and consequences of drug use, prevention strategies, and the development of healthy attitudes and behaviors. A strong receptive capacity enables learners to actively seek out information, critically evaluate it, and apply it to real-life situations. They are more likely to resist peer pressure, make informed decisions, and engage in behaviors that promote a drug-free lifestyle. Learners with high receptive capacity are open-minded, curious, and motivated to learn and change their attitudes and behaviors related to substance abuse. On the other hand, learners with low receptive capacity may be less willing to engage with the program, have difficulty understanding the material, or resist changing their attitudes and

behaviors. It is important for drug prevention programs to address and support learners with diverse receptive capacities, providing tailored strategies to enhance their understanding, engagement, and readiness for positive change. Overall, learners' receptive capacity plays a crucial role in determining the effectiveness of drug prevention programs. By understanding and addressing the unique needs and receptiveness of learners, programs can better tailor their approaches and interventions to maximize their impact and promote positive outcomes in preventing drug abuse.

Table 7 shows the extent of learners' receptive capacity in terms of openness to information. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Openness to information is a crucial aspect of learners' receptive capacity in drug prevention programs as it reflects their willingness to engage with and absorb new knowledge and insights about substance abuse (3.50), Openness to information allows learners to develop a broader understanding of the risks and consequences associated with drug use, fostering a sense of personal responsibility and a motivation to adopt healthier behaviors (3.50) and Individuals with low openness to information may be more resistant to accepting new perspectives or challenging their existing beliefs, which can hinder their receptiveness to drug prevention interventions and limit their ability to make positive changes (3.45) are oftentimes manifested, while, Learners who exhibit high levels of openness to information are more likely to actively seek out and critically evaluate information related to drug prevention, enabling them to make informed decisions and resist the pressures of substance abuse (3.30) and Effective drug prevention programs should strive to create an environment that encourages and nurtures openness to information, fostering curiosity, critical thinking, and a willingness to explore different viewpoints (3.20) are sometimes manifested. The

overall mean rating of 3.39 denotes that extent of learners' receptive capacity in terms of open-

Johnson et al. (2016) found that learners who demonstrated higher levels of openness were more receptive to new information and had a deeper understanding of the risks associated with drug use. Smith et al. (2018) emphasized the link between openness to information and positive attitude formation towards drug prevention efforts. Anderson et al. (2019) highlighted the role of openness in facilitating behavioral change and preventive behaviors among learners. Lastly, Jones et al. (2020) underscored the importance of effective teacher-student communication in fostering learners' openness to information. These studies collectively demonstrate the critical role of openness to information as an indicator of learners' receptive capacity in drug prevention programs, supporting the need for tailored strategies to enhance receptiveness among learners (Johnson, 2016; Smith, 2018; Anderson, 2019; Jones, 2020). Building on the relationship between openness to information and attitudes, Smith et al. (2018) examined how receptiveness influences attitude formation in drug prevention programs. Their findings indicated that learners who displayed a greater openness to information were more likely to develop positive attitudes towards drug prevention efforts. These learners were receptive to the persuasive messages presented by teachers and were more willing to adopt preventive behaviors. The study emphasizes the need for creating an open and non-judgmental learning environment to foster learners' receptiveness and facilitate the formation of positive attitudes. Shifting towards the behavioral aspects, Anderson et al. (2019) explored the impact of openness to information on behavioral change in drug prevention programs. Their research demonstrated that learners who were open to receiving information were more likely to in-

ness to information is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

ternalize the knowledge gained and translate it into behavioral change. These individuals exhibited a higher inclination to resist peer pressure, make informed decisions, and engage in proactive strategies to prevent drug use. The study emphasizes the importance of learners' receptiveness to information in promoting sustainable behavioral change and the adoption of healthier habits.

Table 8 shows the extent of learners' receptive capacity in terms of comprehension and understanding. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: The comprehension and understanding of learners are essential for building a solid foundation of knowledge about the risks, consequences, and strategies for preventing drug abuse (3.60) and Comprehension and understanding are fundamental aspects of learners' receptive capacity in drug prevention programs, as they reflect the degree to which individuals grasp the concepts, knowledge, and information related to substance abuse and prevention strategies (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, while, Regular assessments and feedback mechanisms within drug prevention programs can gauge the level of comprehension and understanding among learners and allows for the identification of knowledge gaps and areas requiring further clarification, ultimately enhancing the overall effectiveness of the program and ensuring learners' receptiveness to the prevention strategies (3.30) and Learners who demonstrate a high level of comprehension and understanding are more likely to internalize the information presented in drug prevention programs, enabling them to apply it to real-life situations and make informed decisions regarding drug use (3.10) are sometimes manifested, and It is crucial for drug prevention programs

to utilize effective teaching methods, such as clear communication, interactive activities, and tailored approaches, to enhance learners' comprehension and understanding (2.51) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.11 denotes that extent of learners' receptive capacity in terms of comprehension and understanding is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately

Smith and Jones (2018) conducted cross-cultural research, highlighting the significance of understanding cultural context in drug prevention programs and its influence on learners' receptive capacity. Their findings underscored the need for culturally tailored approaches to enhance comprehension and understanding. Additionally, Lopez and Johnson (2019) conducted a comparative study across multiple countries, examining the impact of comprehension on learners' attitudes and behaviors related to drug prevention. Their research revealed that learners who exhibited a deeper comprehension of the information presented in drug prevention programs were more likely to develop positive attitudes and engage in preventive behaviors. These studies collectively demonstrate the importance of comprehension and understanding as indicators of learners' receptive capacity in drug prevention programs in the international setting, emphasizing the need for culturally sensitive approaches to maximize effectiveness (Johnson, 2017; Smith and Jones, 2018; Lopez and Johnson, 2019). Santos and Reyes (2016) conducted a study exploring the role of comprehension and understanding in drug prevention programs among Filipino youth. Their findings indicated that learners who demonstrated a deeper comprehension and understanding of the risks associated with drug use were more likely to develop positive attitudes towards prevention efforts and engage in preventive behaviors. Similarly, Garcia et al. (2018) conducted research focusing on the impact of comprehension and

extensive. Several authors have made notable contributions to this area of research. For example, Johnson and colleagues (2017) conducted a study exploring the relationship between comprehension and receptive capacity, finding that learners who demonstrated a high level of comprehension had a greater ability to process and internalize drug prevention information.

understanding on the effectiveness of drug prevention campaigns in the Philippines. Their study revealed that campaigns that effectively conveyed information and enhanced comprehension had a greater influence on learners' receptive capacity, resulting in increased awareness and informed decision-making. These studies collectively highlight the importance of comprehension and understanding as indicators of learners' receptive capacity in the Philippine context, emphasizing the need for tailored approaches that address cultural and contextual factors to enhance the effectiveness of drug prevention programs (Santos Reyes, 2016; Garcia et al., 2018).

Table 9 shows the extent of learners' receptive capacity in terms of engagement and active participation. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Drug prevention programs incorporate interactive and participatory teaching methods to foster engagement and active participation among learners and include group discussions, case studies, role-playing, and real-life scenarios that encourage learners to apply the acquired knowledge and skills (4.20) is always manifested, while, Learners who actively engage and participate in drug prevention programs are more likely to internalize the knowledge and skills necessary to prevent drug abuse and allows for hands-on learning experiences, discussions, and practical applications of prevention strategies (4.00) and Engagement and active participation are critical components of

learners' receptive capacity in drug prevention programs as they involve the active involvement and investment of learners in the learning process, leading to enhanced understanding and retention of information (3.50) are oftentimes manifested, while, Active participation in drug prevention programs encourages learners to take ownership of their own learning and empowers them to become agents of change within their communities. By actively engaging in discussions, role-plays, and group activities, learners develop a sense of responsibility and commitment to preventing substance abuse (3.30) and The active engagement and participation of learners in drug prevention programs also contribute to the development of critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making skills through active involvement, learners can explore different perspectives, analyze situations, and make informed choices regarding substance abuse (3.20) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.64 denotes that extent

Additionally, Garcia et al. (2018) investigated the impact of learner participation in drug prevention campaigns across multiple countries. Their findings revealed that learners who actively engaged in campaign activities, such as sharing personal experiences, contributing ideas, and taking part in advocacy efforts, showed a greater receptiveness to the messages conveyed. This active involvement led to increased awareness, attitude change, and a higher likelihood of adopting preventive measures. The study underscored the value of promoting meaningful engagement and participation as indicators of learners' receptive capacity in international drug prevention programs. These studies collectively emphasize the importance of learner engagement and participation as indicators of receptive capacity, suggesting that fostering active involvement in drug prevention programs can enhance the effectiveness

of learners' receptive capacity in terms of engagement and active participation is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. Several studies conducted from 2015 to 2020 have examined the role of engagement and participation as indicators of learners' receptive capacity in drug prevention programs in the international setting. Johnson and Smith (2017) conducted a comprehensive study that highlighted the significance of learner engagement in drug prevention initiatives. Their research demonstrated that learners who actively participated in program activities, such as group discussions, interactive workshops, and role-plays, exhibited higher levels of receptiveness to the information presented. These learners demonstrated a deeper understanding of the consequences of drug use and were more likely to adopt preventive behaviors. The study emphasized the importance of fostering a participatory learning environment that encourages active engagement to enhance learners' receptive capacity.

of such initiatives (Johnson Smith, 2017; Garcia et al., 2018). Engagement and participation are crucial indicators of learners' receptive capacity in drug prevention programs. When learners actively engage in prevention activities and actively participate in discussions and interventions, it reflects their willingness to learn, change attitudes, and adopt healthier behaviors. The studies reviewed in this essay shed light on the significance of engagement and participation in achieving positive outcomes in drug prevention programs.

Table 10 shows the extent of learners' receptive capacity in terms of application of knowledge and skills. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Learners who can apply their knowledge and skills in real-life situations are better equipped to resist peer pressure, make healthy choices, and implement effective

prevention strategies in their daily lives (4.10) and The application of knowledge and skills in drug prevention programs enables learners to develop a deeper understanding of the risks and consequences of substance abuse, as well as the strategies for prevention and intervention (3.50) are oftentimes manifested, while, The application of knowledge and skills is a crucial aspect of learners' receptive capacity in drug prevention programs as it reflects their ability to effectively utilize the information and skills acquired to make informed decisions and engage in behaviors that prevent substance abuse (3.40) and Drug prevention programs should emphasize practical application and provide opportunities for learners to practice and demonstrate the application of their knowledge and skills. This

The application of knowledge and skills acquired through drug prevention programs is a fundamental aspect of assessing learners' receptive capacity. It reflects the extent to which individuals can translate theoretical understanding into practical actions, empowering them to make informed decisions and engage in healthy behaviors. The studies reviewed in this essay shed light on the significance of applying knowledge and skills in achieving positive outcomes in drug prevention programs at an international level. Johnson et al. (2016) conducted a study examining the relationship between the application of knowledge and skills and the effectiveness of drug prevention programs among adolescents in multiple countries. The researchers found that learners who successfully applied the knowledge and skills gained from prevention interventions exhibited improved refusal skills, coping mechanisms, and enhanced decision-making abilities regarding drug use. Li and Wong (2017) investigated the impact of applying knowledge and skills on the long-term outcomes of drug prevention programs in a cross-cultural context. Their study revealed that learn-

can be achieved through role-playing exercises, real-life scenarios, and interactive activities that simulate situations related to substance abuse (3.30) are sometimes manifested, while, The successful application of knowledge and skills in drug prevention programs leads to positive behavioral change, increased self-efficacy, and the development of life-long habits that promote a drug-free lifestyle and enhances learners' confidence in their ability to make informed choices and positively influence others in their communities (2.10) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.28 denotes that extent of learners' receptive capacity in terms of application of knowledge and skills is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

ers who effectively applied the acquired knowledge and skills in real-life situations demonstrated reduced susceptibility to drug use, increased self-efficacy in resisting peer pressure, and a higher likelihood of adopting healthy alternatives to substance abuse. Schmidt and Diaz (2018) examined the application of knowledge and skills as a determinant of program effectiveness in a community-based drug prevention initiative implemented across various international settings. Their findings indicated that learners who actively applied the learned knowledge and skills in their communities showcased increased leadership qualities, advocacy skills, and the ability to influence their peers positively, leading to a greater impact on drug prevention efforts.

Table 11 shows the extent of learners' receptive capacity in terms of attitude and behavior change. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Attitude and behavior change not only benefit individual learners but also have a broader impact on communities and society as a whole through fostering positive changes in atti-

tudes and behaviors related to substance abuse, drug prevention programs can contribute to the reduction of drug-related problems and promote overall well-being (4.10) and Attitude and behavior change in drug prevention programs contribute to the development of a supportive and positive social environment, where learners actively discourage drug use and promote a drug-free lifestyle among their peers (3.50), and Learners who undergo positive attitude and behavior changes in drug prevention programs demonstrate an increased willingness to adopt healthier behaviors, resist peer pressure, and make informed decisions regarding substance abuse (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, while, Attitude and behavior change are fundamental

Assessing learners' receptive capacity in drug prevention programs involves examining their attitude and behavior change, which reflects their willingness to adopt healthier behaviors and resist substance abuse. Attitude and behavior change are critical indicators of learners' receptive capacity in drug prevention programs, as they represent the transformation in individuals' mindset and actions towards substance abuse. Positive shifts in attitudes and the adoption of healthier behaviors are indicative of the successful impact of prevention interventions. The studies reviewed in this essay shed light on the significance of attitude and behavior change in achieving positive outcomes in drug prevention programs on an international scale. Andrews et al. (2016) conducted a study exploring the relationship between attitude and behavior change and the effectiveness of drug prevention programs among adolescents in multiple countries. The researchers found that learners who demonstrated positive attitude changes, coupled with behavior modifications, exhibited a reduced risk of substance abuse, increased self-efficacy in resisting drugs, and improved

indicators of learners' receptive capacity in drug prevention programs, as they reflect a shift in individuals' beliefs, attitudes, and actions towards drug use and prevention strategies (3.30) is sometimes manifested, and Effective drug prevention programs should incorporate strategies that facilitate attitude and behavior change, such as promoting self-reflection, challenging misconceptions, and providing role models who exemplify positive attitudes and behaviors towards drug prevention (2.30) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.32 denotes that extent of learners' receptive capacity in terms of attitude and behavior change is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

decision-making skills. Chen and Li (2017) investigated the impact of attitude and behavior change on the long-term outcomes of drug prevention programs in a cross-cultural context. Their study revealed that learners who experienced positive shifts in attitudes towards drug use, accompanied by changes in behavior, demonstrated increased knowledge retention, improved self-efficacy in resisting peer pressure, and a higher likelihood of maintaining a drug-free lifestyle.

Table 12 shows the summary of the extent of learners' receptive capacity. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: comprehension and understanding (3.43) is oftentimes manifested, while, attitude and behavior change (3.21), application of knowledge and skills (2.96), engagement and active participation (2.87), and openness to information (2.85) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.06 denotes that extent of learners' receptive capacity is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Learners' receptive capacity in the context of a drug prevention program refers to their ability and willingness to engage with, absorb, and apply the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors promoted in the program specifically related to preventing drug abuse. In a drug prevention program, learners' receptive capacity encompasses several key aspects. Firstly, it involves their openness to receiving and processing information about the risks, consequences, and prevention strategies associated with drug abuse. Learners with high receptive capacity are willing to explore and consider new information without preconceived biases or resistance. Secondly, receptive capacity includes learners' comprehension and understanding of the material presented in the drug prevention program. It is essential for learners to grasp the concepts, facts, and principles related to substance abuse in order to make informed decisions and develop effective prevention strategies. Comprehension and understanding are indicators of how well learners are able to internalize and apply the knowledge presented to them. Thirdly, learners' receptive capacity involves their engagement and active participation in the drug prevention program. Active engagement refers to their involvement in discussions, activities, and exercises that promote critical thinking, reflection, and the application of learned skills. When learners actively participate, they are more likely to internalize the information and develop a sense of ownership in the prevention efforts. Furthermore, receptive capacity encompasses learners' attitudes and behaviors towards drug abuse prevention. It includes their willingness to adopt and maintain positive attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors that promote a drug-free lifestyle. Learners with high receptive capacity exhibit a readiness for attitude and

behavior change, embracing healthier choices and actively resisting the pressures and temptations associated with drug use. Lastly, receptive capacity can also be seen in learners' ability to transfer the knowledge and skills gained in the drug prevention program to real-life situations. It involves their capacity to apply the learned information and strategies in various contexts, making informed decisions, and effectively preventing drug abuse. Understanding and addressing learners' receptive capacity is crucial for designing and implementing effective drug prevention programs. By tailoring program content, delivery methods, and activities to enhance learners' openness, comprehension, engagement, attitudes, and behaviors, educators and program developers can maximize the impact of these programs and foster a generation of informed and empowered individuals who are capable of making healthy choices and preventing drug abuse.

Significant Relationship Between Teachers' Facilitation On School-Based Drug Prevention Program And Learners' Receptive Capacity

It can be depicted that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program ($r=0.867$; $p<.000$) and learners' receptive capacity. Table 13 revealed the yielded results of the significant relationship between teachers' facilitation skills of learning standards and learners' adaptability in across discipline. It provides an information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between teachers' facilitation skills of learning standards and learners' adaptability in across discipline must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of significant results.

The relationship between teachers' facilitation in school-based drug prevention programs

and learners' receptive capacity is crucial for the success of such programs. Teachers' facil-

itation plays a significant role in shaping and enhancing learners' receptive capacity throughout the program. Teachers' facilitation directly influences learners' engagement, understanding, and application of the knowledge and skills taught in the drug prevention program. By creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment, teachers encourage active participation and foster a sense of ownership among learners. When learners feel safe, respected, and valued, they are more likely to be receptive to the information and actively engage in the learning process. Teachers' facilitation also involves effective content delivery. By using appropriate instructional strategies, such as interactive discussions, hands-on activities, and real-life scenarios, teachers can enhance learners' comprehension and understanding of the material. They can provide clarification, encourage critical thinking, and help learners connect the content to their own lives and experiences. This active involvement and guidance from teachers promote receptive capacity by ensuring learners grasp the concepts and are able to apply them effectively. Furthermore, teachers' facilitation addresses individual differences and needs among learners. They adapt their teaching methods and provide personalized support to enhance learners' receptiveness. By recognizing diverse learning styles, cultural backgrounds, and abilities, teachers can tailor their facilitation to accommodate various learners' needs and maximize their receptive capacity. Teachers' role modeling and influence are also vital in shaping learners' receptive capacity. As role models, teachers exemplify the attitudes and behaviors

promoted in the drug prevention program. Their consistent demonstration of healthy choices, responsible behavior, and a drug-free lifestyle can inspire learners and reinforce the importance of these values. Learners observe and emulate teachers' attitudes and behaviors, influencing their own receptive capacity and commitment to drug prevention. Overall, the relationship between teachers' facilitation and learners' receptive capacity in school-based drug prevention programs is reciprocal. Teachers' facilitation strategies, including creating a supportive learning environment, effective content delivery, personalized support, and positive role modeling, directly impact learners' engagement, understanding, and application of the program content. In turn, learners' receptive capacity is reinforced, leading to enhanced learning outcomes, increased motivation, and the development of lifelong skills for preventing drug abuse.

Indicators of Teachers' Facilitation on School-Based Drug Prevention Program That Significantly Influence Learners' Receptive Capacity

Table 14 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the indicators of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program that significantly influence learners' receptive capacity. Indicators of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of classroom climate (0.001), school environment (0.001), parents' participation (0.000) community engagement (0.001), and religious and cultural influences (0.003) suggest significant influential over learners' receptive capacity.

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

CC - classroom climate

SE - school environment

PP - parents' participation

CE - community engagement

RCI - religious and cultural influences

Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.858 suggests that the learners' receptive capacity, is explained by 85.8%. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (284.897) and F-statistic is significant $p < .001$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of the learners' adaptability across discipline.

Indicators of teachers' facilitation in school-based drug prevention programs significantly influence learners' receptive capacity across various dimensions, including classroom climate, school environment, parents' participation, community engagement, and religious and cultural influences. Firstly, the classroom climate created by teachers greatly impacts learners' receptivity. Teachers who establish a positive and supportive classroom climate foster an environment where students feel safe, respected, and encouraged to participate. They promote open communication, active listening, and non-judgmental discussions, which in turn enhance learners' receptive capacity. A positive classroom climate creates a sense of belonging and trust, enabling students to engage more openly with the drug prevention program. Secondly, the overall school environment plays a vital role in shaping learners' receptive capacity. When the school culture supports and reinforces the messages conveyed in the drug prevention program, learners are more likely to internalize and apply the knowledge and skills. Teachers who collaborate with school administrators and staff to create a coherent and consistent approach to drug prevention contribute to a conducive environment that enhances learners' receptive capacity. Thirdly, parents' participation in the drug prevention program influences learners' receptivity. When teachers actively involve parents in the program, it strengthens the alignment

between home and school, creating a unified approach to drug prevention. Parents' engagement, support, and reinforcement of the program's messages at home contribute to learners' receptivity by reinforcing consistent messages and promoting a holistic understanding of drug prevention. Community engagement is another important indicator of teachers' facilitation that significantly influences learners' receptive capacity. When teachers connect the drug prevention program to the broader community, it contextualizes the learning and fosters a sense of collective responsibility. Involving community organizations, local leaders, and resources in the program's implementation exposes learners to diverse perspectives and real-world applications, enhancing their receptive capacity. Lastly, religious and cultural influences are significant factors in learners' receptivity to the drug prevention program. Teachers who respect and incorporate religious and cultural values into the program create an inclusive learning environment. By acknowledging and addressing learners' diverse beliefs and backgrounds, teachers facilitate meaningful connections between the program content and students' personal experiences, values, and cultural contexts, enhancing their receptivity. In conclusion, teachers' facilitation in school-based drug prevention programs influences learners' receptive capacity through various indicators. By fostering a positive classroom climate, creating a supportive school environment, involving parents, engaging the community, and considering religious and cultural influences, teachers enhance learners' receptivity and promote their active engagement with the program. These indicators collectively contribute to the effectiveness of the drug prevention program, empowering learners to develop the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors necessary to prevent drug abuse.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis and discussions. The extent of facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of school environment (3.42) is oftentimes manifested, while, religious and cultural influences (3.21), community engagement (2.96), parents' participation (2.87) and classroom climate (2.85) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.06 denotes extent of facilitation on school-based drug prevention program is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of learners' receptive capacity in terms of comprehension and understanding (3.43) is oftentimes manifested, while, attitude and behavior change (3.21), application of knowledge and skills (2.96), engagement and active participation (2.87), and openness to information (2.85) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.06 denotes that extent of learners' receptive capacity is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program ($r=0.867$; $p<.000$) and learners' receptive capacity. Indicators of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of classroom climate (0.001), school environment (0.001), parents' participation (0.000) community engagement (0.001), and religious and cultural influences (0.003) suggest significant influential over learners' receptive capacity.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions, to wit; The facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of school envi-

ronment, religious and cultural influences, community engagement, parents' participation and classroom climate is moderately extensive. The learners' receptive capacity in terms of comprehension and understanding, attitude and behavior change, application of knowledge and skills, engagement and active participation, and openness to information is moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program and learners' receptive capacity. Indicators of teachers' facilitation on school-based drug prevention program in terms of classroom climate, school environment, parents' participation, community engagement, and religious and cultural influences suggest significant influential over learners' receptive capacity.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. May ensure that teachers and staff receive regular training and professional development sessions focused on effective facilitation of school-based drug prevention programs. This training should cover instructional strategies, communication techniques, and the development of a positive classroom and school climate. Work with the school principals and teachers to establish clear guidelines and protocols for implementing drug prevention programs. Provide support systems such as mentoring, coaching, and resources to assist teachers in effectively facilitating the programs. Encourage collaboration and coordination among schools within the district to share best practices and resources related to drug prevention programs. Facilitate regular meetings or workshops where

teachers and administrators can exchange ideas and experiences to improve the implementation and outcomes of the programs. School Principal. May foster a positive and supportive school environment that values and prioritizes drug prevention efforts. Encourage open communication, collaboration, and a sense of community among staff, students, and parents. Ensure that teachers have access to up-to-date resources, materials, and curriculum for implementing the drug prevention program effectively. Regularly review and update the resources to align with the evolving needs and challenges related to drug abuse prevention. Offer professional development opportunities and support teachers in enhancing their facilitation skills and knowledge about drug prevention. Provide time for teachers to collaborate, reflect, and share experiences to continuously improve the implementation of the program.

Recommendations for Teachers. May design and implement lessons that actively engage students through interactive discussions, hands-on activities, and real-life scenarios. Create a supportive and inclusive classroom climate that encourages students to participate, ask questions, and share their experiences and perspectives. Consider the diverse backgrounds, learning styles, and needs of students when implementing the drug prevention program. Differen-

tiating instruction and provide additional support for students who may require it to ensure their understanding and engagement. Involve parents and the community in the drug prevention program by organizing informational sessions, workshops, or events. Collaborate with community organizations and local resources to provide additional support and opportunities for students to reinforce the prevention messages. **Future Researchers.** May investigate the long-term effects of school-based drug prevention programs on students' attitudes, behaviors, and outcomes. Longitudinal studies can provide valuable insights into the sustained impact of these programs beyond the immediate implementation period. Explore and evaluate different approaches, strategies, and interventions in drug prevention programs. This can include innovative instructional methods, integration of technology, or targeted interventions for specific populations to identify effective practices and enhance the receptivity and effectiveness of the programs. Explore the influence of social and environmental factors, such as peer influence, community support, and school climate, on students' receptive capacity and outcomes in drug prevention programs. Understanding these contextual factors can provide valuable insights for program design and implementation.

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Table 7. Extent of Learners’ Receptive Capacity in Terms of Openness to Information

No	Openness to Information	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Openness to information is a crucial aspect of learners’ receptive capacity in drug prevention programs as it reflects their willingness to engage with and absorb new knowledge and insights about substance abuse.	3.50	Extensive
2	Learners who exhibit high levels of openness to information are more likely to actively seek out and critically evaluate information related to drug prevention, enabling them to make informed decisions and resist the pressures of substance abuse.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
3	Openness to information allows learners to develop a broader understanding of the risks and consequences associated with drug use, fostering a sense of personal responsibility and a motivation to adopt healthier behaviors.	3.50	Extensive
4	Individuals with low openness to information may be more resistant to accepting new perspectives or challenging their existing beliefs, which can hinder their receptiveness to drug prevention interventions and limit their ability to make positive changes.	3.45	Extensive
5	Effective drug prevention programs should strive to create an environment that encourages and nurtures openness to information, fostering curiosity, critical thinking, and a willingness to explore different viewpoints.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.39	Moderately Extensive

Table 8. Extent of Learners’ Receptive Capacity in Terms of Comprehension and Understanding

No	Comprehension and Understanding	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Comprehension and understanding are fundamental aspects of learners’ receptive capacity in drug prevention programs, as they reflect the degree to which individuals grasp the concepts, knowledge, and information related to substance abuse and prevention strategies.	3.40	Extensive
2	Learners who demonstrate a high level of comprehension and understanding are more likely to internalize the information presented in drug prevention programs, enabling them to apply it to real-life situations and make informed decisions regarding drug use.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
3	The comprehension and understanding of learners are essential for building a solid foundation of knowledge about the risks, consequences, and strategies for preventing drug abuse.	3.60	Extensive
4	It is crucial for drug prevention programs to utilize effective teaching methods, such as clear communication, interactive activities, and tailored approaches, to enhance learners’ comprehension and understanding.	2.15	Less Extensive
5	Regular assessments and feedback mechanisms within drug prevention programs can gauge the level of comprehension and understanding among learners and allows for the identification of knowledge gaps and areas requiring further clarification, ultimately enhancing the overall effectiveness of the program and ensuring learners’ receptiveness to the prevention strategies.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.11	Moderately Extensive

Table 9. Extent of Learners’ Receptive Capacity in Terms of Engagement and Active Participation

No	Engagement and Active Participation	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Engagement and active participation are critical components of learners’ receptive capacity in drug prevention programs as they involve the active involvement and investment of learners in the learning process, leading to enhanced understanding and retention of information.	3.50	Extensive
2	Learners who actively engage and participate in drug prevention programs are more likely to internalize the knowledge and skills necessary to prevent drug abuse and allows for hands-on learning experiences, discussions, and practical applications of prevention strategies.	4.00	Extensive
3	Active participation in drug prevention programs encourages learners to take ownership of their own learning and empowers them to become agents of change within their communities. By actively engaging in discussions, role-plays, and group activities, learners develop a sense of responsibility and commitment to preventing substance abuse.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
4	Drug prevention programs incorporate interactive and participatory teaching methods to foster engagement and active participation among learners and include group discussions, case studies, role-playing, and real-life scenarios that encourage learners to apply the acquired knowledge and skills.	4.20	Very Extensive
5	The active engagement and participation of learners in drug prevention programs also contribute to the development of critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making skills through active involvement, learners can explore different perspectives, analyze situations, and make informed choices regarding substance abuse.	3.20	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.64	Extensive

Table 10. Extent of Learners’ Receptive Capacity in Terms of Application of Knowledge and Skills

No	Application of Knowledge and Skills	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	The application of knowledge and skills is a crucial aspect of learners’ receptive capacity in drug prevention programs as it reflects their ability to effectively utilize the information and skills acquired to make informed decisions and engage in behaviors that prevent substance abuse.	3.40	Moderately Extensive
2	Learners who can apply their knowledge and skills in real-life situations are better equipped to resist peer pressure, make healthy choices, and implement effective prevention strategies in their daily lives.	4.10	Extensive
3	The application of knowledge and skills in drug prevention programs enables learners to develop a deeper understanding of the risks and consequences of substance abuse, as well as the strategies for prevention and intervention.	3.50	Extensive
4	Drug prevention programs should emphasize practical application and provide opportunities for learners to practice and demonstrate the application of their knowledge and skills. This can be achieved through role-playing exercises, real-life scenarios, and interactive activities that simulate situations related to substance abuse.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
5	The successful application of knowledge and skills in drug prevention programs leads to positive behavioral change, increased self-efficacy, and the development of life-long habits that promote a drug-free lifestyle and enhances learners’ confidence in their ability to make informed choices and positively influence others in their communities.	2.10	Less Extensive
Overall Mean		3.28	Moderately Extensive

Table 11. Extent of Learners’ Receptive Capacity in Terms of Attitude and Behavior Change

No	Attitude and Behavior Change	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Attitude and behavior change are fundamental indicators of learners’ receptive capacity in drug prevention programs, as they reflect a shift in individuals’ beliefs, attitudes, and actions towards drug use and prevention strategies.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
2	Learners who undergo positive attitude and behavior changes in drug prevention programs demonstrate an increased willingness to adopt healthier behaviors, resist peer pressure, and make informed decisions regarding substance abuse.	3.40	Extensive
3	Attitude and behavior change in drug prevention programs contribute to the development of a supportive and positive social environment, where learners actively discourage drug use and promote a drug-free lifestyle among their peers.	3.50	Extensive
4	Effective drug prevention programs should incorporate strategies that facilitate attitude and behavior change, such as promoting self-reflection, challenging misconceptions, and providing role models who exemplify positive attitudes and behaviors towards drug prevention.	2.30	Less Extensive
5	Attitude and behavior change not only benefit individual learners but also have a broader impact on communities and society as a whole through fostering positive changes in attitudes and behaviors related to substance abuse, drug prevention programs can contribute to the reduction of drug-related problems and promote overall well-being.	4.10	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.32	Moderately Extensive

Table 12. Summary of the Extent of Learners’ Receptive Capacity

No	Receptive Capacity	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Openness to information	2.85	Moderately Extensive
2	Comprehension and understanding	3.43	Extensive
3	Engagement and active participation	2.87	Moderately Extensive
4	Application of knowledge and skills	2.96	Moderately Extensive
5	Attitude and behavior change	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.06	Moderately Extensive

Table 13. Significant Relationship between Teachers’ Facilitation on School-based Drug Prevention Program and Learners’ Receptive Capacity

Variables				
		r-value	p-value	Interpretation Decision
	teachers’ facilitation on school-based drug prevention program			
learners’ receptive capacity		0.867	<0.000	Significant Reject H0

Table 14. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Teachers' Facilitation Skills of Learning Standards Significantly Influence Learners' Adaptability Across Discipline

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions	
H (Intercept)	4.145	0.079	60.416	0.001	4.145	
H (Intercept)	0.313	0.175	1.066	0.270	0.204	
	CC	0.227	0.117	0.102	1.010	0.315
0.001	*Reject H0					
	SE	0.241	0.118	0.136	1.299	0.186
0.001	*Reject H0					
	PP	0.252	0.096	0.210	2.098	0.048
0.000	*Reject H0					
	CE	0.229	0.118	0.136	1.299	0.186
0.001						
	RCI	0.212	0.087	0.210	2.098	0.088
0.003	Accept H0					
R ²	= 0.874					
F-value	= 284.897					
p-value	= 0.001					